

Stress Concentrations in Cylidrically Orthotropic Plates with Radial Variation of the Compliances

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ABSTRACT

The stresses are calculated in a circular composite plate with a central circular hole in which the material is cylindrically orthotropic and the compliances vary with distance from the center. A numerical example shows that an arrangement of the fibers at predominantly + 45 degrees to the radii in the neighborhood of the hole reduces significantly the stress concentrations in an otherwise quasi-isotropic plate.

INTRODUCTION

The first solution of the problem of stress concentration along the edge of a circular hole in a flat plate subjected to uniform uniaxial tension was published by Kirsch (1) in 1898. The stress concentration factor is usually defined as the maximal value of the circumferential stress along the hole divided by the value σ of the uniaxial tensile stress far away from the hole. This value was found to be 3 in the case of an infinite plate made of a uniform isotropic material.

In the 1930s and 1940s Muskhelishvili (2), Lekhnitskii (3), Savin (4), Green (5), and Taylor (6) showed that the stress concentration factor can be much larger when the material of the plate is anisotropic. This theory was summarized by Lekhnitskii (7) and by Green and Zerna (8). The case of cylindrical orthotropy was treated by Hoff (9) in 1981.

The stresses in an infinitely long isotropic strip of finite width were analyzed by Howland and Stevenson (10) in 1933, and Hong and Crews (11) presented the results of finite-element calculations for the stress-concentration factors in finite rectangular plates orthotropic in a Cartesian system of coordinates in 1979.

*The work was carried out under Grant No. NGL 33-018-033 awarded to Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute by the U.S. Air Force Office of Scientific Research and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA Technical Officer: Michael A. Greenfield). The present paper is part of a thesis submitted by Ch. Muser in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of Doctor of Engineering. N.J. Hoff served as thesis advisor.

The results of Hong and Crews and those of Hoff are comparable only in the degenerate case when the material is isotropic. The curves plotted for this case in (9) show that there is little difference between the stress-concentration factors calculated by Hoff for a circular plate of outer radius R and those obtained by Hong and Crews for a rectangular plate of width $2R$ and length $20R$. The Howland values agree completely with those of Hong and Crews.

The agreement among the results of the three different calculations indicated that in uniaxial tension the stress-concentration factor depends mainly on the arrangement of the fibers in the vicinity of the hole, and much less on the size of the plate and the shape of its outer boundary. For this reason it is worth while to use the theory in investigating what changes in the fiber directions in the neighborhood of the hole (without an alteration of the fiber arrangement in the field far away) are likely to lower the stress-concentration factors.

The present paper is a report on such an investigation undertaken at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute. More details can be found in (12).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The stress distribution will be studied in a thin circular plate of radius $r = R$ which has a centrally located hole of radius $r = 1$ (see Fig. 1). The plate is loaded in uniform uniaxial tension of intensity σ along the outer boundary while the inner boundary (that is the edge of the hole) is free of tractions.

Figure 1 General Geometry

It is assumed that the plate is in a state of plane stress. The conditions of equilibrium are satisfied if the stresses are calculated from a stress function ϕ according to the equations:

$$\sigma_r = (1/r)(\partial\phi/\partial r) + (1/r^2)(\partial^2\phi/\partial\theta^2); \quad \sigma_\theta = (\partial^2\phi/\partial r^2) \tag{1a;b}$$

$$\tau_{r\theta} = (1/r^2)(\partial\phi/\partial\theta) - (1/r)(\partial^2\phi/\partial r\partial\theta) \tag{1c}$$

The boundary conditions are uniform uniaxial tension on the outer boundary and no tractions on the inner boundary:

$$\sigma_r = \tau_{r\theta} = 0 \quad \text{when } r = 1 \tag{2a}$$

$$\sigma_r = (\sigma/2) + (\sigma/2)\cos 2\theta; \quad \tau_{r\theta} = -(\sigma/2)\sin 2\theta \quad \text{when } r = R \tag{2b;c}$$

These conditions suggest a solution ϕ_{tot} in the form of a sum of a non-axisymmetric solution ϕ_n and an axisymmetric solution ϕ_a (13):

$$\phi_{tot} = \phi_n + \phi_a \tag{3}$$

For convenience the subscripts n and a are omitted unless they are needed to avoid misunderstandings.

The boundary conditions for the non-axisymmetric part are:

$$\sigma_r = \tau_{r\theta} = 0 \quad \text{when } r = 1 \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_r = (\sigma/2)\cos 2\theta; \quad \tau_{r\theta} = -(\sigma/2)\sin 2\theta \quad \text{when } r = R \quad (4b;c)$$

The boundary conditions for the axisymmetric part are:

$$\sigma_r = 0 \quad \text{when } r = 1; \quad \sigma_r = \sigma/2 \quad \text{when } r = R \quad (5a;b)$$

The constitutive equations are:

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij}^* (1 + \rho_{(i)(j)} r^h) \sigma_j \quad i, j = r, \theta \quad () : \text{no sum} \quad (6a)$$

$$\gamma_{r\theta} = S_{66}^* (1 + \rho_{66} r^h) \tau_{r\theta} \quad (6b)$$

This form of the constitutive equations makes it possible to prescribe the compliances at both boundaries and yet it leaves some flexibility in the choice of their variation between boundaries. (in 1963 Bert and Niedenfur (14) used compliances of the form $S_{ij} = \text{const.} r^h$ in their study of flywheels.) The multiplier ρ_{ij} is defined as:

$$\rho_{ij} = S_{ij}^+ / S_{(i)(j)}^* \quad () : \text{no sum} \quad (7)$$

Where quantities S_{ij}^* and S_{ij}^+ are related to values of the compliances at $r = 1$ and at $r = R$ through the equations:

$$S_{ij}^* = \frac{S_{ij} r=R - R^h S_{ij} r=1}{1 - R^h}; \quad S_{ij}^+ = \frac{S_{ij} r=1 - S_{ij} r=R}{1 - R^h} \quad (8a;b)$$

The stress functions Φ must satisfy the compatibility conditions. Written in terms of strain they are for the non-axisymmetric part of the solution (a comma followed by an index denotes partial differentiation with respect to a coordinate):

$$\epsilon_{r,\theta\theta} - r\epsilon_{r,r} + 2r\epsilon_{\theta,r} + r^2\epsilon_{\theta,rr} - \gamma_{r\theta,\theta} - r\gamma_{r\theta,r} = 0 \quad (9)$$

and for the axisymmetric part:

$$\epsilon_r - \epsilon_\theta - r\epsilon_{\theta,r} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Further it will be convenient to introduce the following ratios in the calculations:

$$\bar{S}_{ij}^* = S_{ij}^* / S_{\theta\theta}^*; \quad \bar{S}^* = 2\bar{S}_{r\theta}^* + \bar{S}_{66}^*; \quad \bar{C}^* = 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^* - n^2 \bar{S}^* \quad (11a;b;c)$$

$$\bar{S}_{ij}^+ = S_{ij}^+ / S_{\theta\theta}^+; \quad \bar{S}^+ = 2\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ + \bar{S}_{66}^+; \quad \bar{C}^+ = 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^+ - n^2 \bar{S}^+ \quad (12a;b;c)$$

SOLUTION OF THE NON AXISYMMETRIC PART OF THE PROBLEM

For greater generality $n\theta$ will be used as the angle rather than 2θ but $n=2$ when the boundary conditions are as given in equations (4).

The solution for the non-axisymmetric part written in form of a stress function is:

$$\Phi_n = \cos n\theta \sum_{p=1}^4 A_p \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} K_p^m r^p \quad (13)$$

Since the stress function is given as an infinite series the compatibility condition (9) must be satisfied in the limit, and the process must converge. The

coefficients K_p^m have to be calculated from the compatibility equation (9) which is written in terms of strain. The strains can be expressed by means of stresses with the aid of relations (6). The stresses are calculated from the stress function derivatives of Eq. (13) according to Eqs. (1). Hence it is possible to write the compatibility equation (9) in series form. Since every non-zero element of the compliance matrix has two powers of the radius r which differ by h , the m -th term of the compatibility equation also has two powers of r which differ by h . One of those powers appears a second time in the $(m+1)$ th term, and the other appears a second time in the $(m-1)$ th term. To satisfy the compatibility equation, the sum of the coefficients of like terms must vanish. This condition yields the recursion formula given below for the coefficients of the infinite series appearing in Eq. (13):

$$K_p^{m+1} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} K_p^m (W/F) \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} W = & t_p^4 + t_p^3 [2h(2m+1) - 4] + t_p^2 [h^2(6m^2 + 6m + 1) - h(12m + 5 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+) + 4\bar{C}^+] + t_p \{2h^3(2m^3 + 3m^2 + m) \\ & - h^2[12m^2 + 10m + 1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+(2m+1)] + h[8m + 2 + \bar{C}^+(2m+1) - 2\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+] - 2\bar{C}^+\} + h^4 m^2 (m+1)^2 \\ & - h^3 m [4m^2 + 5m + 1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+(m+1)] + h^2 m [2(2m+1) + \bar{C}^+(m+1) - 2\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+] - 2hm\bar{C}^+ \\ & + n^2 \{ (n^2 + h - 2)(1 - \bar{C}^+) + \bar{S}^+ [h - 1 - n^2(n^2 + h - 2)] - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+(h^2 - h) \} \end{aligned} \quad (15a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F = & t_p^4 + t_p^3 [4h(m+1) - 4] + t_p^2 [6h^2(m+1)^2 - 12h(m+1) + 4\bar{C}^*] + t_p \{4h^3(m+1)^3 - 12h^2(m+1)^2 \\ & + 8h(m+1) + 2\bar{C}^* [h(m+1) - 1]\} + h^4(m+1)^4 - 4h^3(m+1)^3 + 4h^2(m+1)^2 + \bar{C}^* [h^2(m+1)^2 \\ & - 2h(m+1)] + n^2 \{ (n^2 - 2)(1 - \bar{C}^*) - \bar{S}^* [1 + n^2(n^2 - 2)] \} \end{aligned} \quad (15b)$$

The starting values K_p^0 are chosen to be unity.

The roots $t_p = x_p + iy_p$ can be found from the compatibility equation for the case of homogenous material properties as given by Hoff (9):

$$t_1 = 1 + \alpha; \quad t_2 = 1 + \beta; \quad t_3 = 1 - \alpha; \quad t_4 = 1 - \beta \quad (16)$$

The quantities α and β can be calculated from:

$$\alpha^2 = c + d; \quad \beta^2 = c - d \quad (17a;b)$$

$$c = (1/2)(1 + \bar{S}_{rr}^* + n^2 \bar{S}^*); \quad d^2 = [(1/4)(1 + \bar{S}_{rr}^* + n^2 \bar{S}^*)^2 - (n^2 - 1)^2 \bar{S}_{rr}^*] \quad (18a;b)$$

The roots t_p can be real or complex depending on the numerical values of the quantities c and d . The following three cases have to be treated:

The root t_p is real when $d^2 > 0$ and $c > 0$. This implies that the quantities α and β are real.

$$t_1 = 1 + \sqrt{c+d}; \quad t_2 = 1 + \sqrt{c-d}; \quad t_3 = 1 - \sqrt{c+d}; \quad t_4 = 1 - \sqrt{c-d} \quad (19)$$

In the remaining two cases the root t_p is complex. When $d^2 > 0$ and $c < 0$, the quantities α and β are pure imaginary. The corresponding roots t_p are given as:

$$t_p = x_p + iy_p; \quad x_p = 1; \quad y_1 = -y_3 = \sqrt{-d-c}; \quad y_2 = -y_4 = \sqrt{d-c} \quad (20)$$

On the other hand, when $d^2 < 0$, α and β are complex. In this case the roots t_p can be obtained from the following relations:

$$t_p = x_p + iy_p; \quad x_1 = x_3 = 1 + \kappa; \quad x_2 = x_4 = 1 - \kappa; \quad y_1 = y_4 = \lambda; \quad y_2 = y_3 = -\lambda \quad (21)$$

where λ and κ are given as:

$$\kappa = \{(1/2)(c + \sqrt{c^2 - d^2})\}^{1/2}; \quad \lambda = \{(1/2)(-c + \sqrt{c^2 - d^2})\}^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

This results from the following relation:

$$\alpha = \kappa + i\lambda; \quad \beta = \kappa - i\lambda \quad (23)$$

The constants A_p still have to be determined. The expressions for the stresses can be obtained from Eqs. (13) and (1). The constants A_p can be calculated numerically from boundary conditions (4).

SOLUTION OF THE AXISYMMETRIC PART OF THE PROBLEM

When \bar{S}_{rr}^* is no unity, the solution looks very much like the real solution for the non-axisymmetric case:

$$\phi_a = \sum_{p=1}^2 a_p \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} k_m^p r^{t_p + hm} \quad (24)$$

The two roots t_p are the ones given by Hoff (9) for a homogenous material:

$$t_1 = 1 + \sqrt{\bar{S}_{rr}^*}; \quad t_2 = 1 - \sqrt{\bar{S}_{rr}^*} \quad (25)$$

The coefficients k_m^p are determined in the same manner as the corresponding ones for the non-axisymmetric case. The only change is that the compatibility equation (10) valid for the axisymmetric case is used. The recursion formula for the coefficients is:

$$k_p^{m+1} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} k_p^m (w/f) \quad (26)$$

The quantities w and f are given as:

$$w = h^3 m^3 + h^2 m^2 (3t_p + h - 2) + hm [3t_p^2 + 2t_p (h - 2) + h(\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ - 1) + 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^+] + t_p^3 + t_p^2 (h - 2) + t_p [h(\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ - 1) + 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^+] \quad (27a)$$

$$f = h^3 m^3 - h^2 m^2 (3t_p + 3h - 2) + hm [3t_p^2 + 2t_p (3h - 2) + 3h^2 - 4h + 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^*] + t_p^3 + t_p^2 (3h - 2) + t_p (3h^2 - 4h + 1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^*) + h^3 - 2h^2 + h(1 - \bar{S}_{rr}^*) \quad (27b)$$

The starting value k_p^0 was chosen to be unity. The two constants a_p are readily obtained from the two boundary conditions (5).

The solution includes logarithmic terms when the constant \bar{S}_{rr}^* is unity. Three cases have to be treated depending on the numerical value of the parameter h .

1. When $h \neq \{-2, 0, +2\}$; $\bar{S}_{rr}^* = 1$, then the solution is:

$$\phi_a = a_1 (r^2 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \ell_m r^{hm+2}) + a_2 (\ell_n r + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} k_m r^{hm}) \quad (28)$$

where the coefficients are determined from the following equations:

$$k_{m+1} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} k_m \frac{h^2 m^3 + hm^2 (h+2) + hm(\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ - 1)}{h^2 m^3 + hm^2 (3h-2) + m(3h^2 - 4) + h^2 - 2h}; \quad (29a)$$

$$\lambda_{m+1} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} \lambda_m \frac{h^2 m^3 + h m^2 (h+4) + m(3h+4) + 2 + \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ (hm+2)}{h^2 m^3 + h m^2 (3h+4) + m(3h^2 + 8h+4) + h^2 + 4h+4}; \quad (29b)$$

$$k_1 = -\rho_{\theta\theta} [(\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ - 1)/(h^2 - 2h)]; \quad \lambda_0 = 1 \quad (29c;d)$$

2. When $h = -2$; $\bar{S}_{rr}^* = 1$ then the solution is:

$$\phi_a = a_1 \{ \lambda_{nr} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} k_{-2m} r^{-2m} \} + a_2 \{ r^2 + e(\lambda_{nr}) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} r^{-2m} (b_{-2m} + \lambda_{-2m} \lambda_{nr}) \} \quad (30)$$

The coefficients are given as follows:

$$b_{-2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} (b_{-2m} s_{-2m} - \lambda_{-2m} q_{-2m}) \quad (31a)$$

$$b_{-2} = \rho_{\theta\theta} [3 + 8\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ + 5(\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)^2]/16 \quad e = -\rho_{\theta\theta} (\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ + 1) \quad (31b;c)$$

$$k_{-2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} k_{-2m} s_{-2m}; \quad k_{-2} = \rho_{\theta\theta} (1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)/8 \quad (31d;e)$$

$$\lambda_{-2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} \lambda_{-2m} s_{-2m}; \quad \lambda_{-2} = \rho_{\theta\theta}^2 [1 - (\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)^2]/4 \quad (31f;g)$$

$$s_{-2m} = [2m^3 + 4m^2 + m(1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)]/[2m^3 + 8m^2 + 10m + 4] \quad (32a)$$

$$q_{-2m} = [6m^2 + 8m + (1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+) - s_{-2m} (6m^2 + 16m + 10)]/[4m^3 + 16m^2 + 20m + 8] \quad (32b)$$

3. When $h = 2$; $\bar{S}_{rr}^* = 1$, then the solution is found to be:

$$\phi_a = a_1 \{ \lambda_{nr} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \lambda_{2m} r^{2m} \lambda_{nr} + \sum_{m=2}^{\infty} b_{2m} r^{2m} \} + a_2 \{ r^2 + \sum_{m=2}^{\infty} k_{2m} r^{2m} \} \quad (33)$$

and the corresponding constants are:

$$b_{2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} (b_{2m} s_{2m} + \lambda_{2m} q_{2m}); \quad b_4 = -\rho_{\theta\theta} \lambda_2 (3 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)/16 \quad (34a;b)$$

$$k_{2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} k_{2m} s_{2m}; \quad k_4 = -\rho_{\theta\theta} (\bar{S}_{r\theta}^+ + 1)/8 \quad (34c;d)$$

$$\lambda_{2(m+1)} = -\rho_{\theta\theta} \lambda_{2m} s_{2m}; \quad \lambda_2 = \rho_{\theta\theta} (1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)/2 \quad (34e;f)$$

$$s_{2m} = [2m^2 - (1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+)]/[2m^2 + 4m + 2] \quad (35a)$$

$$q_{2m} = [6m^2 - (1 - \bar{S}_{r\theta}^+) - s_{2m} (6m^2 + 8m + 2)]/[4m^3 + 8m^2 + 4m] \quad (35b)$$

CONVERGENCE

All the series solutions presented converge absolutely when the following conditions are satisfied:

$$(S_{\theta\theta} / S_{\theta\theta})_{r=R} > (1 + R^h)/2 > 1/2 \quad \text{when } h < 0 \quad (36a)$$

$$(S_{\theta\theta} / S_{\theta\theta})_{r=R} < 2/[1 + (1/R)^h] < 2 \quad \text{when } h > 0 \quad (36b)$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The stresses were calculated in a graphite epoxy plate of $R = 10$. The unidirectional properties of the material were taken as (15):

$$E_1 = 1.17 \times 10^{11} \text{ N/m}^2; \quad E_2 = 1.17 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2; \quad G_{12} = 4.48 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2; \quad \nu_{12} = 0.21$$

It was assumed that at the edge of the hole the fibers were arranged at $(\pm 45^\circ)_S$ degrees to the radial direction, and that this arrangement changed gradually to a $(0^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ arrangement at the outer edge of the plate. The exponent h was taken as 2.

The variation of the circumferential stress σ_θ with the radius r is shown in Figure 2 for the plate with varying compliances as well as for the isotropic plate and for a plate in which the fibers are at $\pm 45^\circ$ degrees everywhere. The curves show that the introduction of the $(\pm 45^\circ)$ fiber arrangement in the vicinity of the hole in an otherwise quasi-isotropic plate is very effective in reducing the stress concentrations. The curves also show that the maximal value of the circumferential stress is not at the edge of the hole but inside the plate. However, this value is only about one-half the maximum in the isotropic case.

Figure 2 Circumferential Stress at $\theta = \pm\pi/2$ in Function of Radius r for Different Fiber Arrangements

In Figure 3 the variation with r of the circumferential, radial and the shear stress is shown for the graphite epoxy plate with varying compliances.

Figure 3 Circumferential Stresses, Radial Stresses at $\theta = 0$ and at $\theta = \pi/2$ and Shear Stress at $\theta = \pi/4$ in Function of Radius r

COMMENTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The analysis presented makes it possible to calculate the stresses in a cylindrically orthotropic plate which has a circular hole at its center and is subjected to a uniform uniaxial traction when the elastic properties vary along the radius. Such a variation can reduce the stress concentrations substantially

even though the plate has quasi-isotropic properties near the outer edge. It is believed therefore that the overall properties of a plate can be prescribed at some distance from the hole and nevertheless low stresses can be obtained at the edges of the hole if the material properties are varied suitably.

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